

THE REGISTERED STUDENT NGOS: LIMITATIONS UNDER MALAYSIAN LAWS AND CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Numerous local youth NGOs, including the student organizations are registered under the Registrar of Youth Societies (ROY), a statutory body under the Ministry of Youth and Sports, Malaysia. Several national legislations are enacted by the Parliament to govern their registrations and activities. The purpose of this research is to analyse and study the regulations prescribed under these statutes which they are bound to, after their associations are registered under ROY as well as the challenges that they encounter currently. A number of approaches are used in this research such as the literal interpretation by referring to dictionaries and articles; a descriptive study on related Federal Acts; and interviews with the local student NGOs' leaders. Results suggested that student NGOs' activists do not enjoy absolute freedom of association as these legislations are restricting their activities alongside facing several challenges nowadays. Therefore, a reassessment on these laws is necessary to ensure the stipulated regulations are suitable to the current circumstances in the country.

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1. Introduction

‘Nonetheless, the youths, ever since then, remain as the core pillar of the people’s resurgence. They are the secret of the power of any resurrection; also, the youths are also who bear the banners of any struggles.’

Hassan al-Banna

In this globalization era, the principles of human rights become the main guide in ensuring the sustainability of human species around the globe. It is because every single man is equal in terms of basic human dignity, responsibilities and obligations, without any prejudice on the grounds of colour, sex, language, political affiliation, race, social status, religious belief or other considerations.[1] At the first place, the standards of basic rights prescribed under various local and international documents may either be bound or not based on the legal status of that particular document. Moreover, the freedom of association is one of the crucial fundamental rights safeguarded by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948 and Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam 1990 which also adapted by numerous countries through their constitutions. In Malaysia, the freedom of association for all citizens is legally protected under Article 10(1)(c) of the Federal Constitution of Malaysia 1957; the supreme law of the country. Nevertheless, it is still subjected to the federal laws enacted by the Malaysian Parliament by virtue of Article 10(2)(c) of the Constitution. Furthermore, the associations in Malaysia consist

of the political parties, labour unions, civil societies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) et cetera. To be more specific, the non-governmental organisations are the common platform for the citizens to get involved in volunteerism and additionally, some NGOs are managed by local students who are currently or formerly studying either at local or foreign higher education institutions. Their organizations surely have their own causes, ideologies and objectives which they are struggling to realize it for the sake of the nation's betterment. However, these student societies' movements are restricted under several national laws alongside facing other current challenges. Therefore, the Malaysian students are not enjoying absolute freedom of association as their NGOs' registrations and activities are restricted.

2. The Significance and Roles of Student NGOs

First and foremost, 'student NGO' term is not widely used compared to student movement in describing the student organizations. It is because not all local student movements are registered under the Registrar of Youth (ROY); a statutory body under the Ministry of Youth and Sports, Malaysia. Consequently, under this section, the term 'student movement' will be used to describe the student NGO as both of them are still managed by students and not by other people.

2.1. NGO and Student Movement: The Terms' Description

Generally, a non-governmental organization (NGO) can be defined as a non-profit organization that operates independently of any government, typically one with purpose to address a social or political issue.[2] Besides, Ngo.org [3] defines NGO as any non-profit, voluntary citizens' group which is organized on a local, national or international level. Likewise, the non-governmental organizations (NGOs) which also called "civilians organizations", are societies formed by persons working across national borders to affect public policy.[4] Additionally, World Bank [5] describes NGO as an organization which is not associated to political parties, usually involved in working for the community aid, development and welfare. Thus, there are several definitions that are used to describe non-governmental organization (NGO).

With regard to the definition of student movement, Oxford Dictionaries [6] defines it as a political or protest movement representing the views or ideals of students, especially university students. Additionally, it is also described as designation given to the ideas and activities of student groups involved in social protest.[7] Besides, Kazuko [8] states a student movement is explained by its participants as a sustained, concerned action, exerted by a group or groups of students, opposed to the existing system or systems of power while Hanna [9] describes it as the involvement of students in action that is often campus based or organized from campus, and often this action related to demands and incidences that impacted on the lives of the students who were enrolled at the institutions. In other words, this term can also be translated into Malay as *gerakan mahasiswa* or *gerakan pelajar*. [10] Hence, the term 'student NGO' can be considered as a part of student movements as the word 'organization' in the NGO acronym itself still have the same meaning with the term.[11]

2.2. Early History of Student Movements in Malaysia

In the past, the student movement in Malaysia has its origins before the Second World War. In the early 1930s, teacher trainees from the Sultan Idris Training College (currently known as

Sultan Idris Education University) established the *Kesatuan Melayu Muda* (KMM/ Young Malay Union in English). The purpose of establishing this student movement is to oppose the British colonialism and struggling for the country's independence.[12] Likewise, there are another two prominent student movements which still exist until today. In particular, those societies are the *Gabungan Pelajar Melayu Semenanjung* (GPMS/Peninsular Malay Students Association in English) and *Persatuan Kebangsaan Pelajar Islam Malaysia* (PKPIM/National Union of Malaysian Muslim Students in English). GPMS was established on August 14th and 15th, 1948 while PKPIM was founded 13 years later on March 31st, 1961. Both student movements share the common principle in struggling for the betterment of Islam, Malay and the motherland itself in terms of intellectualism and education. As the matter of fact, majority of the members of these societies consist of Malaysian Malays who are also Muslims. At this point of time, GPMS and PKPIM are examples of two local student NGOs which are registered under the Malaysian Registrar of Youth Societies (ROY) that are essential for them in executing their agendas without any hassle compared to other student movements which are unregistered under ROY.

2.3. Importance of Student Movements and Voices towards Socio-Intellectual Progress

It is undeniable that the emergence of student movements at the campus and among the society has more pros compared to its cons. Historically speaking, they have brought a number of positive changes in the academic world itself alongside struggling for the equal justice, education and rights for every single member of the society irrespective of their religion, ethnicity and colour.[13] Moreover, it is also rooted from their nature of having the leisure time to discuss and elaborate ideas and organize within the university boundary; and the community tends to be supportive towards the students' interests.[14] Plus, they also played a key role in the anti-war movement through the establishment of Stop the War societies in lots of campuses with the objective to oppose the occupation and war along with the Islamic associations that resist the Islamophobia influence among the civilians.[15] Besides, their ideas to improve their learning environment should also be considered. It is because when the student association voices out its opinions, the inclusion of those particular views contributes progressively to an institution's culture as majority of them are recognized in terms of capabilities and standards.[16] As a result, the idea sharing platform provided for them is beneficial as a part of solution, instead of associating them with the campus problems. Therefore, these conditions illustrate the importance of student organizations to play their roles in solving current issues alongside the difficulties faced by their institution's administration.

3. Student NGO as a Part of Youth Movements: Restrictions under Local Laws

As previously stated, the freedom of association among the Malaysian citizens, in particular, the students are regulated by several federal laws enacted by the Parliament; the federal legislature of the country. Under this section, we will go through the statutory provisions on the registrations and activities of student NGOs in Malaysia.

3.1. Youth Societies and Youth Development Act 2007 (Act 668)

In general, this Act is the principal law that governs the youth and student organizations in Malaysia. Its preamble [17] describes the Act as follows:

‘An Act to register youth societies, promote and facilitate the development of youth in Malaysia from the aspect of education, research and human resource, to establish a National Youth Consultative Council, to establish the Malaysian Institute for Research in Youth Development and to provide for related matters.’

Furthermore, according to Section 2 of the Act 668, the term ‘youth’ is defined as a person not less than fifteen years old and not more than forty years old. Based on this provision, the students can also be impliedly classified as the youth too. It is because most of them are the post-secondary and university students who have interest in joining the student NGOs. To be more specific, it supports the finding of the UNESCO [18] that these groups of students are usually between the age of 18 and 22 years old. Moreover, the definition of youth society is also stated under Section 2 of the Act too. It is described as any society which fulfils the criteria like having a name that contains the word “youth” or its synonyms; the age of all members are between fifteen and forty years old and has the aim to organize youth activities. As the student association or NGO has fulfilled these conditions, it shall be registered also under the Registrar of Youth Societies as specified under Section 7(2) of Act 668. In fact, in obtaining the GPMS membership, it also requires the same age prerequisite with the Act which only a Malaysian Malay Student who aged between fifteen and forty years old is eligible to join the NGO.[19] Once the student NGOs have been registered under ROY, they are bound to several restrictions prescribed under the Act 668. For instance, any member who commits several criminal acts within the society is liable to be prosecuted and punished [20] alongside prohibited from becoming the NGO’s advisers, office-bearers or employees on the grounds of conviction of any offence under the Act or any other law, undischarged bankrupt, marked under any order of detention, restriction, supervision or restricted residence by virtue of any law relating to public order or security in Malaysia et cetera.[21] Moreover, their associations’ registration can be cancelled by the Registrar by virtue of Section 20(1) alongside their activities could also be suspended on the ground of necessities in terms of its own or public interest as provided under Section 20(3) of the Act.

3.2. Universities and University Colleges Act 1971 or UUCA (Act 30)

In addition, this statute is another critical legislation that also states several restrictive provisions on the student organizations and activities within the public universities and university colleges, excluding the *Universiti Teknologi MARA* (UiTM). According to Section 15(1) of the UUCA which was amended in 2012, it authorizes the students to join any club, society, association and organization, including political parties. For another thing, another significant provision under this Act is that the students are also allowed to issue any statement relating to their study or research and expressing it at any symposium, seminar or similar event which is organized by a lawful society. Nevertheless, they are still restrained from associating with any unlawful society within or outside the country, the society that the university administration thinks that it is not suitable to the well-being and interest of the students or the University itself or involving themselves in any political party activity inside the campus. In fact, the activities of ROY-registered student NGOs within the campus are also bound to be regulated by the campus management too.

Besides, the student organizations that are established under the university’ constitution are not permitted to show sympathy or support towards any illegal or unauthorized associations

along with collecting the money from the students.[22] If they act which the university administration considers as detrimental towards the interest of the students or the campus itself or against any written law, the Vice-Chancellor of the university may suspend or dissolve the student NGO's branch or other student associations that have been registered under the campus administration after the right to make written representation or statement is given.[23] Based on these statutory provisions, it is realized that the campus management is given the power to control the student organizations and activities within the university and university college's boundaries as similar to ROY that is authorized to regulate the student NGOs nationwide. In conclusion, these legal provisos are inappropriate as they restrict the students from expressing their views on current international issues and limit them from exploring the academic world.[24]

3.3. Educational Institutions (Discipline) Act 1976 (Act 174)

In the third place, this Act has no much difference compared to UUCA in terms of providing regulations on student associations and activities. It is only distinguished with regards to the enforcement which it is applicable to numerous local public educational institutions such as UiTM, Institutes of Teacher Education (IPG), matriculation colleges, polytechnics and community colleges. Primarily, this statute also has provisions which constrain the students or their organizations from joining any illegal society, expressing support or sympathy to them and their movements shall be regulated by the institution management.[25] Moreover, the Executive Head of the institution is granted the power to suspend or dissolve any student organization within the campus too if he thinks that such organizations are detrimental towards the students or institution's interest after he provides them the chance to issue a written statement.[26] With regards to these legal stipulations, although the students NGOs have been registered under ROY including their campus branches, they are still bound to the rules prescribed by the institution in order to carry out any activity within the campus. If the Executive Head orders the campus branch of such student NGO to be suspended or dissolved, it only applies to the branch and not the organization wholly but it still have to be given the chance to make statement in black and white. Hence, through the analysis of stated statutory provisions above, these federal legislations seem limiting the absolute freedom of registered youth associations, in particular, the student NGOs in determining its own drives and activities although they are legally registered under ROY.

4. Contemporary Issues and Challenges Among Registered Student NGOs

In Malaysia, every single student NGO has different causes, objectives or agendas to be achieved and realized. It is significant as the local students can benefit the NGO as the platform to express their opinions and enhance their soft skills in order to contribute towards the nation's betterment. Nonetheless, they will surely have to confront numerous challenges and tribulations from time to time as the country becomes more progressive and globalized. Therefore, the discussion on present-day student NGOs' challenges that are based on the interviews with their leaders will be explained further below.

4.1. Struggling to Stay Relevant

First and foremost, the National Union of Malaysian Muslim Students is struggling to maintain its relevance at this point of time [27] as it is considered as one of the oldest student NGOs in

Malaysia because it has achieved 57 years old since its establishment in 1961. It is because some students nowadays seem lacking of interest in joining intellectual-based NGOs and it causes a gap between PKPIM and other Malaysian students who are its main stakeholder. However, until now, PKPIM still becomes the frontline NGO which represents local students' voices in various issues such as advocating UUCA amendment on students' freedom of association [28], JPA scholarships suspension [29], students' involvement in ISIS [30] et cetera. Consequently, the mechanism taken by its leaders to solve this problem is by reforming and improvising the way of engagement with local students in order to close the gap between them.

4.2. Social Stigma

Besides, the Peninsular Malay Students Association or GPMS is also facing one of the common problems among student NGOs which is the social stigma. This is because some citizens think that this student society has affiliation with a local political party.[31] This problem occurred due to the misunderstanding of its agendas and ideologies that are closely related with that particular political organization. Because of that, its activists are struggling to organize motivational programmes with school students as they have to receive permission from the District Education Office in order to execute such events which are regarded as one of its well-known agendas to promote quality education among the Malay students. Hence, although this prominent student NGO faces such stigma, it is undeniable that the programmes carried out by GPMS have succeed in advocating education awareness among the Malays until they become more progressive in terms of intellectual until today.

4.3. Commitment Problem Among Activists

Additionally, another current problem faced by registered student society is the lack of commitment given by its activists. *Kesatuan Pelajar Islam Johor* (KPIJ/Johore Muslim Students Association in English); one of the PKPIM affiliated NGOs confronts such issue when it comes to organize an internal event called *Ketika Hewi Berbicara* (Once Young Lady Speaks) [32] which is regarded as the platform for its female activists to enhance their communication skills alongside increasing their confidence level through public speaking or forum. It happens due to short number of active members to execute such event as most of them are studying or working outside of their own state; Johore. Therefore, this issue can only be solved when the activists are responsible towards their duties within the organization and it (KPIJ) or any other student NGOs cannot be blamed because of inefficiency as its leaders and members that should take responsibility to ensure their associations remain active although facing individual or collective difficulties.

4.4. Reception of Political Pressure

Likewise, the student NGOs also encounter political pressure in executing their agendas and GPMS is one of them which suffered this common issue.[33] Although the government administrators were changed during the 14th General Election, it is still run under political pressure as same as before. In fact, *Banglo GPMS* (GPMS Bungalow), its headquarters also is not fully-owned by the NGO as the specified property is built under government-owned land. Consequently, this condition sometimes limits their movement from being independent from government intervention and political influence. In solving this issue, GPMS leaders have made

a decision to not relying much on government funding by looking for alternative funding sources as to ensure their NGO sustainability.

4.5. Culture of Fear

Last but not least, this phrase describes a theory which dreads are normally manipulated to achieve political goals.[34] Such concept is widely affected among local student NGOs' activists due to existing hierarchical system that confines them from enjoying their freedom of speech by expressing their views and opinions without being worried of the consequences.[35] Moreover, this situation also happens when the NGO veterans are lacking of trusts towards the current generation who succeeding them in achieving their noble aspirations. Subsequently, the youth leaders who inherited the organization leadership could not execute their plans effectively as they feel intimidated by their seniors who sometimes intervene with their efforts.

Conclusion

In a nutshell, the registered student NGOs' activists in Malaysia do not enjoy absolute freedom of association alongside the freedom of speech. This conditions can be said to be caused by the restrictions imposed through several federal Acts as discussed above. It is undeniable that these laws are restricting the student activities within and outside of their campuses. Additionally, nowadays, some of the student organizations are facing several contemporary challenges that either caused by the statutory limitations or other current situations that are happening in this country. Therefore, a reassessment on these legislations is necessary to ensure the specified regulations are suitable to the current circumstances in Malaysia along with reducing the student NGOs' burdens when they execute their plans. Hopefully, the activism space provided by the government can be benefitted by the local student NGOs in order to empower Malaysian youths as aspired by the Ministry of Youth and Sports.

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